

Factors Affecting Green Purchase Behavior of Bangladeshi Consumers

Shofiqul Islam^{1*}

¹ School of Economics and Management, Shaanxi University of Science and Technology, Xi'an, China,
Email: shofiq362@gmail.com

Accepted December 17, 2021

Published December 23, 2021

*Corresponding Author:

Shofiqul Islam

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799810>

Pages: 87-102

Funding: N/A

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Shofiqul Islam (2021). Factors Affecting Green Purchase Behavior of Bangladeshi Consumers. *North American Academic Research*, 4(12), 87-102. doi:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5799810>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

1. Introduction

The effect of the unsustainable consumption patterns worldwide poses a serious environmental threat, such as alarming global warming and frequent climate change, driving out people to reshape their usual living pattern. It is obvious that the consumer's choice pattern on goods and services have equal direct and indirect effects on the ecological betterment (Gruber & Schlegelmilch, 2014). As soon as the business firms endorse any successful green marketing ideas and eco-friendly marketing plans, consumers tend to follow that and act accordingly paying premium prices to the path of pro-environmental manner and sustaining green consumerism (Polonsky

ABSTRACT

The severe environmental pollution and its harmful effects on mankind are intensely due to the unsustainable consumption of products and services supplied by the business firms. The main purpose of this study is to identify the factors affecting the green purchase behavior of ecofriendly products. The study is of exploratory in nature and focuses on hypothesis testing using structured questionnaire and interviews. Structured questionnaire is used to collect primary data from a sample size of hundred respondents in convenience sampling methods. The survey population represents the people who go for shopping; data have also been collected from the point of purchase of the shopping malls and other places. The Likert Scale question with five-scale rating was used to do the hypothesis testing. The questions included closed ended questions related to the green consumer behavior. The research explored that environmental attitude, perceived seriousness of environmental problems and government initiatives are the significant factors predicting the green consumer behavior in Bangladesh. Thus the government should play a proactive role in educating consumers as well as supporting green initiatives of business houses with extended cooperation and enforcement of policy actions.

Keywords: FACTOR ANALYSIS, GREEN CONSUMERISM, GREEN PRODUCTS, PURCHASE BEHAVIOR

& Rosenberger, 2001).

Green consumerism is the consideration to which consumers' shows a preference toward pro-environmental products (Matthes and Wonneberger 2014). It indicates the ecological consider consumption comprises of lower consumption, green buying and reduced pollution (Hoffmann & Schlicht, 2013; Lin & Hsu, 2015). From the social marketing viewpoint, green consumerism refers to the motivational tendency of each consumer (Moisander, 2007) and ensure a balance the social problems in which personal, societal and environmental interests are in conflict(Gupta & Ogden, 2009; Schuitema & de Groot, 2015).

Bangladesh once regarded as the most backward countries with prone to natural calamities and acute poverty has been growing towards the middle income country featuring with the high growth rate (around seven percent), fulfilling development indicators and faster digital revolution. In the parallel race of development, the natural degradation becomes a new problem which is endangering the forthcoming generations. Although the country adopted Sustainable development goal (SDG) with implementing many Millennium development goals (MDG) in many promising old sectors like Ready Made Garments (RMG), the fishing sector, cement, glass, brick, ceramic industries. The banking sector is supplying opportunities in the form of green finance and banking. The energy sector, which is considered as the most polluters progressed a lot in the form of eco-friendly manner. The emergence of renewable resources like rapid solar electrification, use of bio-technology and energy efficient products is showing prospects for the environmental sustainability. The heavy industries are using effluent treatment plants (ETP), recyclable ingredients; improved waste management system along with the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) certified building technology gradually. The government banned polythene bags using the Bangladesh Environment Conservation Act 1995 and perusing producer, consumers adopt the jute made bags. Bangladeshi scientists with the patronization of the government invented single use, cheaper biodegradable plastic bags (Sonali Bag) from the locally available ingredients like Jute which is expected to use for other industrial products gradually to meet up the standard green packaging (Islam R. 2019).

There are some debates over whether consumer support green brand or they purchase as randomly. The numerous research finding conducted by the past researcher presented a clash result each other. Gruner (1993) concluded that an insignificant portion of consumers follow the environmental concern and it results their purchase behavior. Although many ecofriendly products are characterized with quality ingredients, yet it may be difficult for them to change their old taste and habits at once. Thus the survey outcome revealed that at least 8% respondents accepted green products eyeing on Eco benefits (Our Green World, 2008). This outcome is supported by the study of Nik Abdul Rashid (2009) who commented that it is not necessarily certain that consumers would buy a green product even though they are knowledgeable and conscious about the environment. Alwitt & Bergers (1993) refute that many environmentally aware people do not buy a green product or service. So it is essential to know that whether environmental concern people behave in a positive manner towards the buying of green product or not.

In contrast, many studies (Chase & Smith, 1992; Abdul Wahid et al. 2002; Polanski & Rosenberger 2001) found

the correlated behavior among the environmental awareness and its buying behavior. They believe that separating green and non-green could benefit to the producers. Thereby, it is high time to know the other environmental factor that influence consumer to purchase green products. This study holds that the past conflicting results may arise due to the geographical, demographic and cultural context. Thus, this study would like to conduct the research based on the high purchasing power and who buy from a supermarket in the context of Bangladesh.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Green Products:

The words sustainable, pro-environmental, sustainable, ecological, eco-friendly, green products has been used as an alternative by the marketer to aware and promoting their consumers in the green marketing campaign for the last decade (Gosavi, 2013). Eco-friendly products postulate a product or services harmless to the outdoor broader environment. Therefore, the U.S. Federal Trade Commission (FTC) took actions, warning marketers to supply environmentally safe products for more than a decade ago. Environmentally safe indicates the no short term and long term harms on our natural habitat and for the natural wealth of future generations to come. Thus the green product is that product which was manufactured with the toxic-free elements and environmentally-friendly mechanisms, meaning no polluting activities and which is certified from authorized agencies in favor of environmental branding (Kumar and Ghodeswar, 2015). The researchers Tseng & Hung, (2013) presented numerous criteria mention in Rahman, (2018) to be a green product such as easily reused, made using natural and/or renewable resources, Contains recycled content, readily recycled, biodegradable, energy efficient and durable with low maintenance requirements, which is holding as the definition of green product for this study.

2.2 Green Marketing:

Green marketing brings up the concept that a set of activities that are plotted to create and assist the exchange of green products and services aiming at meeting human needs or wants (Polonsky, 2011). This considered as a system which endorse the eco-labeling and publicity of goods and services intended to either cutting down any harmful effects on the ecology. The process of product promotion by green marketing differs based on the product functions, manufacturing procedure, wrapping and advertisement together with the supply chain (Cherian& Jacob, 2012; Polonsky, 2011). However, firms with green marketing strategies would concentrate on the design, promotion, and setting up price, together with the distribution of goods to promote environmental protection (Polonsky, 2011) which is also viewed as the green marketing mix. The product is the central focus of the green marketing mix and the enormous part of the entire green marketing strategy. Therefore, it should be regarded as brain where ecofriendly goods is not merely the main article consumed, but contains the whole product featuring the material it used, the production process, and its packaging, etc. (Fan and Zeng, 2011).

2.3 Factors influencing the green purchase behavior:

The green buying decision to buy ecofriendly goods is becoming a vibrant issue in current green marketing research. The buying decision can be inherited from the interest of the consumers to go with green enterprises

(Laroche et al., 2001), accomplishing the buying activities (Mishra & Sharma, 2010), implementing a sustainable consumption pattern (Young et al., 2010), and willingness to spend more cash to obtain eco-friendly products (Hasan & Ali, 2015). The following are the proposed factors affecting the green purchase behavior:

Social Influence:

The buyers are the subsets of the interconnected society where they live in. Their buying behaviors are largely affected by the social dynamics (Ryan, 2001) and social norms (Kalafatis et. al. 1999) meaning the togetherness tendency and referent’s points of view respectively. Many buyers have the ability to take their purchase decision solely. Yet, it becomes stronger where they feel their decision matches with their closely connected people such as peer, family members, friends, colleagues and influential people around them. This influence proved more effective than the promotional activities performed by the company itself since they found not self-interest by the referents. Thus, many researchers found the relationship of social influence on the purchase decision. A person advocates a product only when they become convinced about the benefit of it which is evident from the researches like Bearden & Etzol (1982), More, Wilkie & Lutz (2002) Price, Frick & Higie (1987) and Ward and Reingen (1990). The researcher Kim & Choi (2005) found that collectivism has significant influence on the consumer green buying behavior. Likewise, the researchers (Bearden and Etzel (1982); Moore, Wilkie, and Lutz (2002); Price, Feick, and Higie (1987); Ward and Reingen (1990) found the similar results, while Ryan (2001) concluded that a peer influence can lead people towards greener products. And Baker et al (2008) proved that social influence has strong connection with the ecofriendly products. So, the following hypothesis can be developed:

H1a: There is a positive relationship between social influence and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Figure-1: Conceptual Framework of the green purchase behavior

Environmental Attitude:

The term attitude refers to the extent to which a person imply to a favorable or an unfavorable appraisal of the behavior in question (Ajzen 1991). Likewise, environmental attitude indicates the favorable or unfavorable judgment towards the environmental burning issues. Environmental attitude can be separated as altruistic

(concern over others), self-centered and eco-centric (concern for the environment) attitude. Attitude is a widely accepted predictor of consumer willingness to pay for environmental products. For many consumers who have the solvency to avail products, price becomes a secondary factor choosing a product among ecofriendly and non ecofriendly products over the environmental issues (Laroche et al. 2001; Chyong et al. 2006). If the conscious consumers feel that their purchase of non-ecofriendly products may cause environmental degradation, they rethink about their purchase provided that the availability of the alternatives in the market. Thus, the following hypothesis can be drawn:

H2a: There is a positive relationship between Environmental Attitude and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Environmental Concern:

Environmental concern designates the degree to which people are conscious about the environmental problems and readiness to solve them Alibeli and Johnson (2009). While Lee (2008) defined this as the extent of emotional involvement in environmental matters. Even this involvement could be dormant. According to Aman et al. (2012) Environmental concern indicates the emotional disposition of consumers i.e., anger towards degradation of nature. Various authors linked environmental concern to environmental friendly behavior (Irawan & Darmayanti, 2012; Aman et al., 2012; Albayrak et al., 2013). As per Irawan and Darmayanti (2012), green consumer behavior is highly affected by the environmental concern within the Indonesian university students. Whereas Albayrak et al. (2013) found in his research in Turkey that environmental concern is the strong predictor of behavioral intention and Aman et al. (2012) revealed that environmental concern has significant impact on the purchase intention of Sabahan consumers. Thus higher the level of environmental concern, the higher the consumer purchase intention and this will foster green purchase behavior. So, the following hypothesis is held:

H3a: There is a positive relationship between environmental Concern and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Perceived seriousness of environmental problems:

The perception of any person to the intensity, harmfulness and gravity of environmental matters and problems could touch his or her green purchasing behavior. This indicates those who are not ecofriendly consumers behave differently than the green consumers having a belief that these problems would be solved automatically and vice-versa. While the green buyer's takes immediate action as it may cause serious impact on the health and quality of life. Guber's model (1996) mixed the 'perceived seriousness of environmental problems' with two other issues of environmentalism to pinpoint policy relevant stuffs of environmental concern. Besides, Bord and O'Connor (1997) identified that female were more perceived serious than the male on the ecological problems and anxious about the detrimental impact on their health. Whereas Lee (2008) explored that perceived seriousness is not a significant factor affecting teenagers' ecofriendly behavior because of their insensibility. However, the result may be different in different circumstances. So, the following hypothesis is worth study in Bangladesh perspectives:

H4a: There is a positive relationship between Perceived seriousness of environmental problems and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Perceived Environmental responsibilities:

Perceived Environmental responsibilities signify the personal obligation towards the environmental issues. Sukhdial and Venice (1990) defined it as the degree of a person's perception of self-involvement in safeguarding the environment. Similarly Lai (2000) refers it as an emotional involvement regarding environmental matters. People in many cases try to escape from their own responsibility leaving it to the collective organizations or government or its agencies which Lai (2000) has pointed out in his study in Hong Kong. Besides environmental responsibility is popularly used idea promoting sustainable consumer behavior, it is remaining almost unidentified by the present researches (Wells et al., 2011). Earlier researches examined the intuition of environmental responsibility among Hong Kong people (adults as well as teenagers) (Lai, 2000; Lee 2008, 2009) where they found the sense of responsibility among people on the environmental safeguard duty is adequately weak. They usually expect government rapid action within illicit policies and hesitant to the individual efforts (Lai, 2000; Cherian & Jacob, 2012). Yet, Laroche, Bergeron, and Barbaro-Forle (2001) and Chan (2000) stated that while consumers presume companies and firm to take actions in favor of environment, they expressed their support for sustainability mainly at the time of their purchase. As per Nyborg et al. (2006) who found that the greater the environmentally responsible consumers are, the greater willing they are to buy ecofriendly alternatives. Therefore, it is holding that buyer may adopt ecofriendly products, if firms can inform about their green products in an effective ways. Thus the following hypothesis can be held:

H5a: There is a positive relationship between Perceived Environmental responsibilities and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior:

People are motivated to adopt a particular action or steps when they feel their actions could lead to the achievement of the purpose for which they were active (McClelland, D.C., 1987). Likewise the Perceived consumer effectiveness has commendable effects on the individual behavior, whether such action fosters to the optimum results (Ellen et al. 1991). According to Conner and Armitage, (1998) people attempt to engage in behaviors that they have faith in their ability to understand. Whereas Lee and Holdern (1999) stated that the perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior is the vital predator of green consumer behavior. Buyers who have a greater perceived effect of environmental behavior will lead to becoming eco-friendly buying behavior comprising to buying of sustainable products (Vermeir & Verbeke 2006) organic food (Verhoef 2005) and green products (Kim et al. 2005). Thus Individual participate in actions that they seems will be fruitful (Wigfield and Eccles, 2000), that indicates that buyers will purchase ecofriendly products where they perceive their behavior benefits environmental improvement. It is predicted that higher the perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior, the higher the willingness to buy green products. Therefore, the following hypothesis can be taken for further assessment:

H6a: There is a positive relationship between Perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior and purchase of eco-friendly products.

Government Initiatives:

Environmental sustainability is the broad term which is not possible for any individual people or group to ensure. It needs interactive government initiatives in terms of policy, financial and legislative actions. The term government initiative indicates the cooperation given or proactive action taken any country's national government (Diekmeyer, 2008). They can play a vital role in environmental protection and stopping environmental degradation. For instance, the Bangladesh government has enacted a law in favor of banning polyethylene in long before that was impossible for any individual or groups. An Individual can walk on shoe when the government initiates greater program for environmental protection with the various international donor agencies funded projects. However, the continuous such campaign can also change the buying behavior into pro-environmental from none. As per the study of Tsen, et al. (2006) explored that consumers expect government active role influencing people's buying even though those consumers have adequate sense of environmental matters. In addition, the public need to be directed at realizing the government objectives extending the pattern of consumption and sustainable lifestyle diminishing the environmental degradation in the path of sustainable consumption patterns (Yahya, W. K. et al. 2013). The researchers (Wang et al., 2011; Gillingham and Palmer 2013; Reynolds et al., 2012) found that government initiative such as campaign, subsidies, carbon emission tax etc. significantly affect the purchase behavior of consumers. Thus the following hypothesis is drawn.

H7a: There is a positive relationship between Government Initiatives and purchase of eco-friendly products.

3. Methodology

This is an empirical study and exploratory in nature. To identify the factor influencing the green purchase behavior, the study adopted primary data using a survey method in Dhaka city. In the capital city it is relatively easier to get the cautious and learned customer who considers many aspects before their buying. A questionnaire survey was conducted using a structured questionnaire following literature study. The questions were designed mainly in a five-point Likert scale, except for the demographics, as a measurement scale having no open ended questions. A total of 120 respondents were chosen on a random basis following the purposive random sampling methods, but 100 samples were chosen finally after screening out the incomplete questionnaires. The super shops where mainly covered in the survey includes Swapno, Agora, Mina Bazar, and Sonali Bazar along with the survey of educational institutions. For analyzing the data, a factor analysis method using Principal Component Analysis techniques was adopted. It also used a regression analysis method using SPSS software 16 version.

4. Results and discussions

4.1 Demographic profile

The greatest percentage respondents (74%) were male and the majority of the respondents (45%) are postgraduate which is followed by the undergraduate/Degree/Diploma (38%) holders. Around 37% of the respondents are a private service holder and the 30% of the respondents mentioned their profession as a business. Regarding the income level of the respondents, about 61% of the respondents were with the earnings

of 40,000 to 60,000 taka while 19% of the respondents attributed with less than 20,000 taka of income level. Whereas, a majority (55%) of respondents are in the age range between 31 to 40 followed by the age group of 41-50 years (21%) indicating their maturity in commenting on such issue. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondents

Aspects	Classification	Percent	Aspects	Classification	Percent
Gender	Male	74	Income	Up to 20,000	19
	Female	26		20,000-40,000	9
Age	18-25	6		40,000-60,000	61
	26-30	9		60,000-80,000	9
	31-40	55		>80,000	2
	41-50	21	Profession	Govt. employees	15
	51-60	9		Student	14
Educational level	HSC or Equivalent	12		Business	30
	Undergraduate/ Degree/Diploma	38		Private Employees	37
	Postgraduate	45		Housewife	4
	MPhil/PhD	5			

4.2 Factor Analysis:

Factor analysis is a technique to reduce a bulk number of variables into few factors extracting maximum common variance with the assumption that the variables are in a linear relationship and having no multicollinearity (StatisticsSolution, 2020). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test which measure the adequacy of the sample suggests that values over 0.5 are quite good. For this study the KMO is .835 which it is acceptable and the sample is considered as good for further test. While, Bartlett's test measures whether the correlations between variables are sufficiently large for factor analysis to be appropriate (Field, 2005). Here (Table 2), the Bartlett's test is highly significant ($p < 0.001$) and good enough for further analysis as well.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.835
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square
	1501.589
	df
	136
	Sig.
	.000

The principal component analysis of all the 29 variables yielded five factors based on Kaiser's criterion of retaining eigenvalues greater than 1.0 (Field, 2005). Eigenvalues is the characteristic roots displays variance explained by that particular factor out of the total variance (Table 3).

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings(a)
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total
1	7.516	44.211	44.211	7.516	44.211	44.211	5.884
2	2.334	13.727	57.938	2.334	13.727	57.938	5.540
3	1.924	11.319	69.257	1.924	11.319	69.257	4.864
4	1.205	7.088	76.346	1.205	7.088	76.346	2.508

5	1.046	6.150	82.496	1.046	6.150	82.496	3.687
6	.813	4.780	87.276				
7	.376	2.213	89.488				
8	.345	2.032	91.520				
9	.279	1.641	93.161				
10	.263	1.548	94.709				
11	.211	1.240	95.948				
12	.179	1.054	97.002				
13	.152	.894	97.896				
14	.139	.820	98.716				
15	.091	.533	99.249				
16	.082	.485	99.733				
17	.045	.267	100.000				

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

a When components are correlated, sums of squared loadings cannot be added to obtain a total variance.

By Kaiser Criterion, acceptable Eigen Values should have variance equal to 1 at least. In this study, we found eigenvalue of 1 for the five factors. The cumulative Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings indicate the average explanatory power of these factors. The selected factors in this present study have 82.496% of explanatory power which is acceptable as it is greater than the rules of thumbs of 50% (Table 3).

Out of seven factors chosen in the conceptual framework, five factors have been identified initially, namely social influence, environmental attitude, perceived seriousness of environmental problems, perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior and government initiatives. Whereas the factors environmental concern and perceived environmental responsibility were excluded from the analysis (Table 4).

Table 4: Pattern Matrix^(a)

	Component				
	Environmental Attitude	Government Initiatives	Perceived Seriousness of Environmental Problems	Social Influence	Perceived Effectiveness of Environmental Behavior
SI1				.866	
SI3				.837	
SI4				.888	
EA1	.831				
EA2	.861				
EA3	.835				
EA4	.755				
EA5	.922				
PSEP1			.889		
PSEP2			.880		
PSEP3			.884		
PEEB1					.965
PEEB2					.810
GI1		.855			
GI2		.955			
GI3		.852			
GI4		.937			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

a Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

4.2.1 Convergent Validity & Reliability:

The reliability and validity test is essential in factor analysis of the explored factor to justify The correlation value (Table 5) is below 0.8 which indicates no multicollinearity problem among the factors and the factors are convergent valid.

Table 5: Component Correlation Matrix

Component	1	2	3	4	5
1	1.000	.488	.560	.098	.404
2	.488	1.000	.442	.037	.507
3	.560	.442	1.000	.172	.383
4	.098	.037	.172	1.000	.108
5	.404	.507	.383	.108	1.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization.

Alpha (α) Coefficient is used to measure internal consistency of data. The values of Cronbach's alpha (Table-6) for all the factors are above 0.8 which reflects a strong reliability of the factors. Thus all these factors are fit for the further advance analysis.

Table 6: Cronbach's Alpha

Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Social Influence	.841	3
Environmental Attitude	.921	5
Perceived seriousness of environmental problems	.893	3
Perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior	.826	2
Government initiative	.943	4

4.3 Regression Analysis:

The study used linear regression model to identify the amount of relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 7: Regression Model Summary values

Model Summary ^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.855 ^a	.732	.717	.654

a. Predictors: (Constant), GI_AV, SI_AV, PSEP_AV, PEEB_AV, EA_AV

From the model summary (Table-7), it is seen that the R is equal to 0.732 which pronounces a solid relation between independent variables' items and dependent variable's item. This is reflecting that 73.2 percent of changes in the dependent variable's item are described by these independent variables' items. Here, the point is R square didn't involve a degree of freedom in the analysis. Therefore, with using Adjusted R square (which involves df) we have $R^2 - Adj = 0.717$, which is more reliable. Thus, the model for this study is a good fit model.

Table 8: ANOVA^(b)

Mode		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	108.409	5	21.682	50.699	.000(a)
	Residual	39.772	93	.428		

Total	148.182	98		
-------	---------	----	--	--

a Predictors: (Constant), GI_AV, SI_AV, PSEP_AV, PEEB_AV, EA_AV

b Dependent Variable: choose ecofriendly products

ANOVA test is used in the regression analysis to test the influence that independent variables have on the dependent variable. As it can be observed (Table 8), with P-value= 0.000 it can be concluded that the F is significant in 0.01. This is reflecting that at least one of the independent variable questions is effective in predicting the dependent variable.

4.4 Testing of Hypotheses:

The results of this study (see Table 9) state that there were statistically significant and positive relationships between environmental attitudes ($\beta=0.232$, $p<0.01$), Perceived Seriousness of Environmental Problems ($\beta=0.356$, $p<0.01$), government initiatives ($\beta=0.266$, $p<0.01$) and green purchase behavior of consumers. The other relationship between Social Influence ($\beta=0.106$, $p>0.05$), Perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior ($\beta=0.152$, $p>0.05$), and green purchase behavior become insignificant. Therefore, the results supports H2, H4, H7, and hypothesis number one and six were not supported.

Table 9: Test of hypothesis

Hyp	Relationship	Beta	Std. Error	t-value	Decision
H ₁	Social Influence → Green Purchase Behavior	.106	.079	1.345	Not supported
H ₂	Environmental attitude → Green Purchase Behavior	.232	.068	3.420*	Supported
H ₄	Perceived Seriousness of Environmental Problem → Green Purchase Behavior	.356	.067	5.278*	Supported
H ₆	Perceived effectiveness of Environmental Behavior → Green Purchase Behavior	.152	.069	2.206	Not supported
H ₇	Government Initiatives → Green Purchase Behavior	.266	.064	4.144*	Supported

* indicates 1% level of significance,

As hypothesized, Social influence has significant and positive relationship with the green purchase behavior which is found as insignificant in the present study. This is similar to the studies (Irawan and Darmayanti 2012; Tang, S.M., 2014.) and dissimilar to the studies (Jamal, Z.B et al. 2016; Kalafatis et al. 1999); Abdul Wahid et al. 2011). The reason could be that the consumers may not discuss the environmental problems and share about the green products among themselves. The second hypothesis assumed that environmental attitude has positive relationship and the present study confirms a weak but significant relationships. This is consistent with the study of Jamal, Z.B et al. (2016), Axelrod et al. (1993), Berger et al. (1992), and Lee (2008) justifying the relevancy of it. The fourth hypothesis holds that the perceived seriousness of the environmental problem is positively related to the green consumer behavior which is found true in the current study confirming its strong predicting

power among others. This significance is in line with the study of Sinnapan et al. (2011). The next hypothesis estimated that the perceived effectiveness of the environmental problem is positively related to the green purchase behavior and this is found as insignificant in the present study which is inconsistent with the researcher Lee et al. (1999). Finally, the hypothesis seven anticipated that government initiative is positively related to green purchasing behavior and the present study went similarly. However, the result is similar to the study of Tsen et al. (2006) and Sinnappan et al. (2011) and dissimilar to the study of Tang, S.M., (2014).

5. Conclusions

The purpose of the study was to identify the factors affecting the green purchase behavior of the consumers and to ascertain the relationships of these factors with the green purchase behavior. After rigorous analysis of the data, it is found that social influence, environmental attitude, perceived seriousness of environmental problems, perceived effectiveness of environmental behavior are the factors in predicting green purchase behavior out of seven proposed factors. The subsequent regression analysis ended with the result that only environmental attitude, perceived seriousness of environmental problems and government initiatives are significantly related to the green purchase behavior in Bangladesh. Among the significant factor, the perceived seriousness of environmental problems has been found as the strongest predictor in understanding green purchase behavior for eco-friendly products. Thus the research lays a bridging stone for both the managerial and academic people who are involved in policy making and new knowledge generation for the concerned people. In recommendations, the government should play a proactive role in educating consumers to pursue them to purchase more ecofriendly products. Besides, the government and its other agencies should come up with extended cooperation in both the financial and policy matters to continue the green initiatives of business houses. The existing green firms should be protected from inconsistent market competition and other operational barriers by enforcing of lawful actions.

6. Limitations and scope of future study

The study adopted samples from only Dhaka city in purpose which would be better if we can extend those samples throughout the countries especially the divisional cities. Besides, it collected only hundred samples. The future research could be much more productive with such extension of samples size as well as the territories of the study. In addition, the research analyzed its data by using only SPSS software which could be a space for other researches experimenting with other statistical software and techniques such as a Structural Equation model with the help of PLS SEM or AMOS software.

Acknowledgement

The researchers would like to express their gratitude to the anonymous reviewers for their efforts in improving the quality of this paper.

References:

1. Abdul Wahid, N., & Abustan, I., (2002), "Environmental concern: between consumers' awareness and willingness for attitude change", Realizing Agenda21: International Conference on Environmental Management: Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Selangor. pp. 579-590.
2. Ajzen, I (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organization Behavior and Human Decision Process*, 50,179-211.
3. Albayrak, T., Aksoy, Ş. and Caber, M., (2013). The effect of environmental concern and scepticism on green purchase behaviour. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*.
4. Alibeli, M. A., and Johnson C. (2009) Environmental concern: A cross national analysis. *Journal of International and Cross Cultural Studies*, Vol. 3 Issue 1
5. Alwitt, L.F. and Berger, I.E., (1993). Understanding the Link Between Environmental Attitudes and Consumer Product Usage: Measuring the Moderating Role of Attitude Strength. *Advances in consumer research*, 20(1).
6. Aman, A.L., Harun, A. and Hussein, Z., (2012). The influence of environmental knowledge and concern on green purchase intention the role of attitude as a mediating variable. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 7(2), pp.145-167.
7. Axelrod, L. J., & Lehman, D. R. (1993). Responding to environmental concern: What factors guide individual action? *Journal of Environmental Psychology* 13, 149-159.
8. Baker, J. P., & Ozaki, R. (2008). Pro-environmental products: Marketing influence on consumer purchase decision. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 25(5), 281- 293.
9. Bearden, W. O., & Etzel, M. J. (1982). Reference group influence on product and brand purchase decisions. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 9, 183-194.
10. Bearden, W. O., & Etzel, M. J. (1982). Reference group influence on product and brand purchase decisions. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 9, 183-194.
11. Berger, I. E., & Corbin, R. M. (1992). Perceived consumer effectiveness and faith in others as moderators of environmentally responsible behaviors. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 11, 79-89.
12. Bord, R. J., & O'Connor, R. E. (1997). The gender gap in environmental attitudes: The case of perceived vulnerability to risk: Research on the environment. *Social Science Quarterly*, 78(4), 830-840.
13. Chase, Dennis and Therese Kauchak Smith (1992), "Consumers Keen on Green but Marketers Don't Deliver," *Advertising Age*, 63 (June 29), s2-s4.
14. Cherian, J., & Jacob, J. (2012). Green marketing: A study of consumers' attitude towards environment friendly products. *Asian Social Science*,8(12), 117–126.
15. Chyong, H. T, Phang, G, Hasan, H. & Buncha, M. R. (2006). Going green: A study of consumers' willingness to pay for green products in Kota Kinabalu. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 7(2), 40-54.
16. Conner, M. and Armitage, C.J., (1998). Extending the theory of planned behavior: A review and avenues for further research. *Journal of applied social psychology*, 28(15), pp.1429-1464.
17. Diekmeyer, P. (2008). Bribery in Public Procurement: Protecting Your Company from Corruption Bribery in Public Procurement: Methods, Actors, and Counter-Measures.
18. Ellen P, Wiener J, Walgren C. (1991). The role of perceived consumer effectiveness in motivating environmentally conscious behaviours. *Journal of Public Policy and Marketing* 10(2): 102–117.
19. Fan, H. and Zeng, L., (2011). Implementation of green marketing strategy in China: A study of the green food industry.
20. Field, A. (2005). *Discovering Statistics Using SPSS*. London: SAGE Publications. Retrieved on September 2018.
21. Gillingham, K. and Palmer, K., (2013). Bridging the energy efficiency gap. Resources for the Future discussion paper, pp.13-02.

22. Gosavi PS (2013). Gaining competitive advantage through green marketing of cell phone. *ASM's International E-Journal of Ongoing Research in Management and IT*, 13(1): 1-11.
23. Gruber, V., & Schlegelmilch, B. B. (2014). How techniques of neutralization legitimize norm- and attitude-inconsistent consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121(1), 29–45.
24. Guber D. 1996. Environmental concern and the dimensionality problem: a new approach to an old predicament. *Social Science Quarterly* 77(3): 644–662.
25. Gupta, S., & Ogden, D. T. (2009). To buy or not to buy? A social dilemmaperspective on green buying. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 26(6),376–391.
26. Hasan, Z., & Ali, N. A. (2015). The impact of green marketing strategy on the firm's performance in Malaysia. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 172(27), 463-470.
27. Hoffmann, S., & Schlicht, J. (2013). The impact of different types of concernment on the consumption of organic food. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 37(6), 625–633.
28. Irawan , R., & Darmayanti , D. (2012). The influence factors of green purchasing behavior: A study of university students on Jakarta. *School of Marketing, Bina Nusantara University- International* , 8.
29. Islam R. (2019) Bangladeshi Scientist Invents Biodegradable Single-Use Bag Made from Jute, *Global Citizen*, Retrieved from: <https://www.globalcitizen.org/en/content/bangladesh-invents-biodegradable-throw-away-bag/> on 11 am, 30/04/2020.
30. Jamal, Z.B., Islam, S. and Barua, P., (2016) Analyzing Factors that Affect Green Purchase Behavior: From the Context of Bangladeshi Consumers, *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, Vol. 4 (10).
31. Kalafatis S. P., Pollard, M., East. R., & Tsogas M. H. (1999). Green marketing and Ajzen's theory of planned behaviour: A cross-market examination. *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 16(5), 441-460.
32. Kim, Y., & Choi, S. M. (2005). Antecedents of green purchase behavior: An examination of collectivism, environmental concern, and PCE. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 32, 592-599.
33. Kumar P and Ghodeswar BM (2015). Factors affecting consumers' green product purchase decisions. *Marketing Intelligence and Planning*, 33(3): 330-347.
34. Lai, O. K., 2000. Greening of Hong Kong: Forms of manifestation of environmental movements. In the dynamics of social movement in Hong Kong. *Hong Kong: City University Press*.
35. Laroche, M., Bergeron, J., & Barbaro-Forleo, G. (2001). Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(6), 503-520.
36. Lee K. (2009). Gender differences in Hong Kong adolescent consumers' green purchasing behavior. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 26(2), 87-96.
37. Lee, J. & Holden, S. J. S. (1999). Understanding the determinants of environmentally conscious behavior. *Psychology & Marketing*, 16(5), 373- 392.
38. Lee, K. (2008). Opportunities for green marketing: Young consumers. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 26(6), 573-586.
39. Lin, H.-Y., & Hsu, M.-H. (2015). Using social cognitive theory to investigate green consumer behavior. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 24,326–343.
40. Matthes, J., and A. Wonneberger. (2014). The skeptical green consumer revisited: testing the relationship between green consumerism and skepticism toward advertising. *Journal of Advertising*, 43 (2):115–127. doi:10.1080/00913367.2013.834804
41. McClelland, D.C., (1987). Human motivation. CUP Archive.
42. Moisander, J. (2007). Motivational complexity of green consumerism. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 31(4), 404–409.
43. Moore, E. S., Wilkie, W. L., & Lutz, R. J. (2002). Passing the torch: Intergenerational influences as a source of brand equity. *Journal of Marketing* 66(2), 17-37.

44. Nik Abdul Rashid. N. R. (2009). Awareness of Eco-label in Malaysia's Green Marketing Initiative. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(8), 132-141.
45. Nyborg, K., Howarth, R.B. and Brekke, K.A., (2006). Green consumers and public policy: On socially contingent moral motivation. *Resource and energy economics*, 28(4), pp.351-366.
46. Our green world (2008): An international survey covering 17 countries into how green we really are. Retrieved February 20, 2013, from http://www.wpp.com/~media/sharedwpp/marketing%20insights/hot%20topics/climate%20change/tns_market_research_our_green_world.pdf
47. Polonsky, M. J., & Rosenberger, P. J., III. (2001). Reevaluating green marketing: A strategic approach. *Business Horizons*, 44(5), 21–30.
48. Price, L. L., Feick, L. F., & Higie, R. A. (1987). Information sensitive consumer and market information. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 21(2), 328-341.
49. Rahman, H.A., (2018). Green consumerism (Kepenggunaan Hijau). *Asian journal of environment, history and heritage*, 2(2).
50. Reynolds, T., Kolodinsky, J. and Murray, B., (2012). Consumer preferences and willingness to pay for compact fluorescent lighting: Policy implications for energy efficiency promotion in Saint Lucia. *Energy policy*, 41, pp.712-722.
51. Ryan, A. M. (2001). The peer group as a context for the development of young adolescent motivation and achievement. *Children development*, 72(4), 1135-1150.
52. Schuitema, G., & de Groot, J. I. M. (2015). Green consumerism: The influence of product attributes and values on purchasing intentions. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*, 14, 57–69.
53. Sinnappan, P. & Abd Rahman, A. (2011). Antecedents of green purchasing behaviour among Malaysian consumers. *International Business Management*, 5(3), 129-139.
54. StatisticsSolution (2020). Factor Analysis, StatisticsSolution, accessed at: <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/factor-analysis-sem-factor-analysis/> on: 5:00Pm, 02/05/2020
55. Sukhdial, I., & Venice, J. (1990). An analysis of green purchasing behavior: Hybrid-electric vehicle adoption at the state level. *Economics & Business Journal*, 39(1).
56. Tang, S.M., 2014. Factors that influence green purchase behaviour of Malaysian consumers (Doctoral dissertation, UTAR).
57. Tsen, C. H., Phang, G., & Hasan, H., & Buncha, M. R. (2006). Going Green: A Study of Consumers' Willingness to Pay for Green Products in Kota Kinabalu. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 7(2), 40-54.
58. Verhoef, P. C. (2005). Explaining purchases of organic meat by Dutch consumers. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 32(2), 245-267.
59. Vermeir, I., & Verbeke, W. (2006). Sustainable food consumption: Exploring the consumer attitude-behaviour gap. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 19(2), 169-194.
60. Wang, Z., Zhang, B., Yin, J. and Zhang, Y., 2011. Determinants and policy implications for household electricity-saving behaviour: Evidence from Beijing, China. *Energy Policy*, 39(6), pp.3550-3557.
61. Ward, J. & Reingen, P. (1990). Sociocognitive analysis of group decision making among consumers. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 17, 245-260.
62. Wells, V. K., Ponting, C. A., & Peattie, K. (2011). Behavior and climate change: Consumer perceptions of responsibility. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 27(7-8), 808–833.
63. Wigfield A, Eccles J. (2000). Expectancy–value theory of achievement motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 25(1): 68–81.

64. Yahya, W.K., Hashim, N.H., Mohamad, S.A. and Ramly, Z., (2013). The relationship between perceived consumer effectiveness, environmental concern and ecologically conscious Consumer behavior. In 3rd Annual International Conference on Business Strategy and Organizational Behaviour (pp. 93-98).

Mr. Islam Doctoral student of Logistics Engineering and Management at Chang'an University (CHD) in Xi'an, China. He completed Master of Business Administration (MBA) from Shaanxi University of Science and Technology (SUST), Xi'an, China. He has also done his Bachelor of Law (LL.B Honors) from Bangladesh University of Science and Technology (BUBT) Dhaka, Bangladesh.

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

